

A Perturbation Theory Based Analysis of Reactivity Feedbacks during a ULOHS Transient in Molten Salt Reactors

Sophie Deanesi¹, Davide Pizzocri¹, Stefano Riva¹, Stefano Lorenzi^{1,*}

¹Politecnico di Milano, Department of Energy, Nuclear Engineering Division

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ABSTRACT

To assess the steady state and dynamic behaviour of molten salt reactors, multidimensional multiphysics simulations prove their advantages in capturing the strong coupling between thermal-hydraulics and neutronics and resolving flow-related phenomena. In homogenous circulating fuel systems, geometric design optimisation plays a crucial role, as abrupt changes in the passage area and sharp edges can induce the formation of recirculation zones and flow oscillations. Furthermore, the resulting flow regimes directly influence neutronic parameters via thermal feedback coefficients and the delayed neutron precursor drift driven by the liquid fuel motion. This work aims at analysing these multidimensional multiphysics phenomena, evaluating the influence of thermal-hydraulic variable variations in response to an accidental transient scenario on the neutronic characteristics of the system. This evaluation compares the outcomes of a Stand Alone OpenFOAM simulation and a coupled OpenFOAM-Modelica simulation based on the primary and outer loops of a Molten Salt Fast Reactor. The standard solver developed at Politecnico di Milano, coupling neutronics and thermal-hydraulics within a unique OpenFOAM environment, is equipped with a module to solve the adjoint flux equations under the multigroup neutron diffusion approximation. Perturbation theory is then applied to assess the local impact of the multidimensional variable distributions on the effective multiplication factor, employing the fluxes and adjoint fluxes evaluated at steady state as well as the results of the transient simulation.

Keywords: Multiphysics Model, Adjoint Flux, Perturbation Theory, Molten Salt Reactors, Accidental Transient

1. INTRODUCTION

When dealing with numerical simulations of nuclear reactors, multidimensional multiphysics models have demonstrated significant advantages for the analysis of the dynamic and steady state reactor behaviour [1]. The possibility of assessing the strong neutronics-thermal-hydraulics coupling, along with flow-related phenomena, is even more relevant when investigating circulating fuel concept, as the Molten Salt Reactor (MSR) [2, 3]. Power production and release in the coolant, precursor drift induced by fuel motion, and strong negative feedback coefficients are phenomena inherent in the MSR concept, which can be properly captured thanks to this modelling approach. This feature is valuable not only in the evaluation of the nominal operating conditions of the reactor, but also in the assessment of the reactor dynamic response under accidental scenarios. The detrimental effects of the failure of primary and outer loop components result in variations in both the shape and magnitude of operating variable distributions, which in turn can trigger thermal feedback effects or alter the spatial distribution of delayed neutron precursors, affecting the reactor operation. Furthermore, the geometrical characteristics of the domain, such as sharp edges and reduced sections at core inlet and outlet, deeply affect the time dependent variable evolution. Consequently, huge efforts are dedicated to refining the core geometry to minimise the formation of stagnation zones and liquid salt oscillations to enlighten the thermo-mechanical loads on containment structures [4]. The modelling of transient scenarios in these

*stefano.lorenzi@polimi.it

kinds of simulations is enabled by imposing time-dependent functions on global parameters representing primary loop components. On the other hand, recently a growing interest was demonstrated in the development of computational chains coupling system codes with multiphysics tools in order to directly include the interaction of primary loops with global plant models. This approach was applied from the for advanced reactors as the Lead Fast Reactor and Molten Salt Reactor [5, 6]. At Politecnico di Milano, a modelling framework is under development coupling multidimensional multiphysics tools with system codes, based on the OpenFOAM-Modelica coupling chain via Functional Mock-Up Interface (FMI).

The motivation of this work arises from a comparison of a transient simulation performed on a Stand Alone OpenFOAM model and on Coupled OpenFOAM-Modelica model. Specifically, the results of an unprotected loss of heat sink (ULOHS) demonstrate a variation in the mean core temperature at which the reactor stabilises at the end of the transient. This final temperature level depends on the power evolution, which is influenced by the modelling assumptions adopted for the primary loop heat exchanger. In these simulations, the primary pumps are considered in working state, hence no reactivity insertion is expected from the delayed neutron precursors hold back. To inspect how the variations in thermal-hydraulic variables affect the neutronic behaviour of the system, perturbation theory is applied to investigate the impact of a non-uniform temperature field on cross sections and diffusion coefficients. Perturbation theory has already been employed to support multiphysics analyses. [7] applied Monte Carlo perturbation to improve convergence in steady state coupled simulations. [8] used Serpent-2 sensitivity methods with FRENETIC for ALFRED reactor studies. More recently, [9] introduced the CAPTAIN framework for coupled heat conduction and point kinetics. The remainder of this work is organised as follows: Section 2 outlines the multiphysics solver with the coupling approach and the formulation of the perturbation theory. In Section 3, the case study is presented, focusing on the primary loop of a MSFR. Section 4 presents and discusses the results of the ULOHS accidental transient scenario.

2. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

2.1. Multiphysics Solver and OpenFOAM-Modelica Modelling Framework

At Politecnico di Milano, steady state and transient solvers coupling neutronics and thermal-hydraulics were developed employing the OpenFOAM toolkit to assess the behaviour of MSRs and model relevant phenomena inherent in liquid fuel concepts [10, 11, 12, 13]. These multiphysics models have recently been equipped with input and output ports enabling data exchange between OpenFOAM and system-code models via FMIs. Within this computational framework, the multidimensional representation of the MSFR primary loop in OpenFOAM is coupled with models of the intermediate salt loop and Balance of Plant, developed in Modelica. Further details on the coupling strategy can be found in [14].

2.1.1. Thermal-Hydraulic Module

For the thermal-hydraulic part of the model, a single-phase incompressible version of the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes equations is implemented. The buoyancy effects are accounted for by the Boussinesq approximation. To mimic the presence of primary pump and heat exchanger, a semi-implicit momentum source and heat sink are included in the temperature and momentum equations. These uniform sources and sinks are characterised by global parameters that can be modulated by imposing time-dependent functions to simulate the failure of components in accidental transient scenarios. In the temperature equation, a volumetric power source is included to account for the contributions given by prompt and delayed fissions, establishing the coupling path from neutronics to thermal-hydraulics.

2.1.2. Neutronic Module

The neutronic module implements the multigroup neutron diffusion approximation, with transport equations for delayed neutrons and decay heat precursors. To compare with the adjoint counterpart, the

steady state formulation of the neutron fluxes and the delayed neutron precursors equations, including the effective multiplication factor k_{eff} , is reported below.

$$-\nabla \cdot (D_{n,g} \nabla \varphi_g) + \left(\Sigma_{a,g} + \sum_{h \neq g} \Sigma_{s,g \rightarrow h} \right) \varphi_g = \frac{1}{k_{eff}} (1 - \beta) \chi_{p,g} \sum_i \bar{v}_i \Sigma_{f,i} \varphi_i + \sum_{i \neq g} \Sigma_{s,i \rightarrow g} \varphi_i + \chi_{d,g} \sum_k \lambda_k c_k \quad (1a)$$

$$\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u}c_k) = \nabla \cdot (D_{eff} \nabla c_k) - \lambda_k c_k + \beta_{d,k} \sum_g \bar{v}_g \Sigma_{f,g} \varphi_g \quad (1b)$$

As previously mentioned, this work implements a module to solve adjoint flux equations under the multigroup neutron diffusion approximation [15]. These adjoint fluxes will then be employed in the evaluation of the effect of cross section variations under an accidental scenario according to the perturbation theory. Both the adjoint flux and adjoint delayed neutron precursor equations are solved in the steady state version of the code.

$$-\nabla \cdot (D_{n,g} \nabla \varphi_g^\dagger) + \left(\Sigma_{a,g} + \sum_{h \neq g} \Sigma_{s,g \rightarrow h} \right) \varphi_g^\dagger = \chi_{d,g} \sum_k \lambda_k c_k^\dagger + \frac{1}{k_{eff}^\dagger} (1 - \beta) \bar{v}_g \Sigma_{f,g} \sum_i \chi_{p,i} \varphi_i^\dagger + \sum_{i \neq g} \Sigma_{s,g \rightarrow i} \varphi_i^\dagger \quad (2a)$$

$$-\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u}c_k^\dagger) = \nabla \cdot (D_{eff} \nabla c_k^\dagger) - \lambda_k c_k^\dagger + \beta_{d,k} \sum_g \bar{v}_g \Sigma_{f,g} \varphi_g^\dagger \quad (2b)$$

To establish the coupling from thermal-hydraulics to neutronics, temperature and density fields are extracted to update the neutronic parameters. Specifically, a linear term in temperature accounts for density variation, consistently with the Boussinesq approximation. Furthermore, a logarithmic term in temperature representing the Doppler effect corrects the reference value $\Sigma_{R,g}^{ref}$ for a generic reaction and the g^{th} group. A similar method is used to update the neutron diffusion coefficients, $D_{n,g}$. The group constants and the coefficients for a reference temperature T_{ref}^Σ are calculated with the JEFF-3.1.1 cross section library [16] in Monte Carlo reactor physics and burnup code Serpent 2 [17].

$$\Sigma_g = \left(\Sigma_g^{ref} + A_g^{ref} \log \frac{T}{T_{ref}^\Sigma} \right) \frac{1 - \beta_T (T - T_{ref})}{1 - \beta_T (T_{ref}^\Sigma - T_{ref})} \quad (3)$$

where T_{ref} is the thermal reference temperature, while T_{ref}^Σ is the neutronic reference temperature. Finally, the steady state version of the neutronic module is equipped with a power iteration routine to evaluate the multiplication factor. The routine solves the k -eigenvalue problem [15] by setting the time derivatives to zero and scaling the mean number of neutron produced per fission by k_{eff} . The value of k_{eff} is updated iteratively and the neutron fluxes are normalised at each time step to achieve criticality at a power level specified by the user.

2.2. Perturbation Theory

To analyse the effect of variations in neutronic parameters induced by the temperature evolution during a transient scenario, perturbation theory is applied, based on the formulation presented in [15].

$$\Delta k_{eff} = k_{eff}^2 \frac{\sum_g \int \left[\varphi_g^\dagger \nabla \cdot (\Delta D_{n,g} \nabla \varphi_g) - \Delta \Sigma_{r,g} \varphi_g^\dagger \varphi_g + \sum_{g'} \Delta \Sigma_{s,g' \rightarrow g} \varphi_g^\dagger \varphi_{g'} + \frac{\Delta (v \Sigma_{f,g})}{k_{eff}} \varphi_g^\dagger \varphi_g \right] dV}{\sum_g \int v \Sigma_{f,g} \varphi_g^\dagger \varphi_g dV} \quad (4)$$

where the removal cross section of group g , $\Delta\Sigma_{r,g}$, accounts for both absorption and scattering events.

To apply this formulation, some considerations need to be introduced. First, the delayed neutron precursors, which could significantly contribute to the variation in the effective multiplication factor due to the drift induced by the liquid fuel, are not treated. This assumption is justified since, in the transient scenario of interest, the primary pumps are considered in a working state, so the precursor hold back is prevented by a fixed flow rate. The only flow rate variation is driven by the temperature variation, but given the forced circulation regime, this contribution can be considered negligible. Secondly, the assumption of small perturbations, introduced in [15] is adopted, whereby, at first order the perturbed flux φ^* can be approximated by the unperturbed one φ , where $\varphi^* = \varphi + \Delta\varphi$. In this work, this assumption is not strictly valid in terms of absolute flux level due to the steep power reduction caused by thermal feedback effects in response to a temperature increase. However, the appropriate application of the perturbation theory was verified *a-posteriori* according to the shape flux variation throughout the transient. Finally, with the awareness that the perturbation theory is meant to calculate a global parameter characterising the whole system, i.e., Δk_{eff} , a cell-by-cell evaluation is initially performed to estimate the local contribution to Δk_{eff} . This allows for the assessment of the multidimensional effects associated with a complex geometry, characterised by recirculation structures and sharp bends.

3. THE MSFR MODEL

The case study presented in this work is based on a 2D axisymmetric wedge representing the MSFR primary loop and developed within the Euratom EVOL project [18]. The domain with regions representing the primary loop components is shown in Figure 1. The thermophysical properties of the fluoride salt, which are considered constant in the model, can be found in [11]. The coupling with the Modelica model, shown in Figure 1, is implemented employing a domain-overlapping approach to model the primary heat exchanger. Specifically, the exchanged variables are the power from the Modelica primary loop and the temperature and flow rate from the primary circuit in OpenFOAM. On the other hand, in the multiphysics simulation, the primary heat exchanger is represented by a volumetric heat sink uniformly distributed in the heat exchanger region, in the form of $q = \gamma (T_{ext} - T)$. γ (W/m^3K) is a tunable parameter that accounts for the global heat transfer coefficient between the primary and outer loops, while T_{ext} (K) is the intermediate loop reference temperature [19]. The parameters characterising the pump and the heat exchanger are tuned to establish a total volumetric flow rate of $4.5 m^3/s$ and a total thermal power produced in the primary loop of $3 GW_{th}$. For the neutronic model, six energy groups for the fluxes and eight and three for the delayed neutrons and decay heat precursors are adopted, respectively. Vacuum boundary conditions are applied at the external and blanket walls.

Figure 1. 2D axial-symmetric EVOL domain subdivided in zones representing the primary loop components (on the left) and the Modelica model employed in the Coupled Case (on the right).

4. UNPROTECTED LOSS OF HEAT SINK: ULOHS

In this work, the MSFR dynamic behaviour is evaluated in response to a deterioration of the heat removal supported by the heat exchanger. This accidental scenario, i.e., unprotected loss of heat sink (ULOHS), can be initiated by a blockage or leakage in the intermediate circuit or a failure of the secondary pumps. The unintended event is assumed to be symmetric and unprotected, so the failure affects all the outer loops equally, and no counteractions are activated to mitigate the harmful consequences of the failure. The primary pumps are assumed to remain in a working state throughout the transient. In the Stand Alone OpenFOAM model, the failures cause a reduction in the overall heat transfer coefficient, γ , and an increase in the intermediate salt temperature, T_{ext} . To account for the inertia of the components undergoing malfunctions, exponential time-dependent profiles are imposed on γ and T_{ext} , with a time constant, $\tau = 5$ s [19]. In the Coupled Case, the failure is directly imposed as a coast-down of the intermediate pump, whose flow rate is reduced down to 30% of the nominal value.

4.1. Results

The outcomes of the simulations demonstrate similar trends for the main operating variables. As a consequence of the deterioration in the heat transfer provided by the primary heat exchanger, the core inlet temperature increases steeply at the beginning of the transient, as shown in Figure 2. This rise leads to an increase in the mean core temperature, triggering the thermal feedbacks, which cause a reduction in the power produced in the primary loop, as illustrated in Figure 2. As the transient evolves, the counteraction of the feedback effects driving the power-to-flow ratio decrease contrasts the inlet temperature increase resulting from the degraded heat transfer, leading to a new steady state. The reduction in the power-to-flow ratio translates into a reduced temperature difference between the outlet and the inlet of the core, evaluated as mean adiabatic mixing temperatures.

Figure 2. Total power produced in the MSFR primary circuit for both cases (on the left). Mean temperature of core, inlet and outlet temperatures with their average for the Stand Alone (centre) and Coupled (right) Case.

For both cases, Figure 2 demonstrates that the mean temperature level is not restored to its nominal value at the end of the accidental scenario, despite no reactivity is inserted in the core, since the precursor hold back is prevented by the imposed flow rate. Furthermore, depending on the modelling approach adopted to represent the primary heat exchanger, both power and temperature stabilise at different levels in the final steady state. To delve into this aspect and to assess the impact of the heat exchanger modelling assumption, Figure 3 illustrates the temperature distributions at the beginning and at the end of the transient. These distributions are characterised by a strong recirculation structure next to the blanket wall, induced by the sharp edge at the core inlet. It is worth mentioning that this geometry was improved to prevent stagnation regions and flow oscillations, and it is still under design optimisation. The proposed methodology is generally applicable to arbitrary geometrical configurations, whose specific features inherently influence the quantitative impact on the results. Moreover, in Figure 3, the distribution of the percentage temperature difference from the beginning to the end of the simulation can be appreciated. It is evident that the presence of a recirculation structure leads to a non-

uniform reshaping of temperature in the core, which is less pronounced for the Coupled Case. For both cases, this non-uniformity justifies the discrepancy between the reduction in the mean temperature of the core, evaluated as an integral volume average, and the increased level of the outlet-inlet mean value deriving from adiabatic mixing temperatures.

Figure 3. Temperature distribution at the beginning (on the left), at the end of the transient (in the centre) and their percentage difference (on the right) for the Stand Alone and Coupled Case.

According to the transient simulation outcomes, the objective is to inspect how variations in temperature distribution influence the neutronic parameters, updated as in Eq. 3. Therefore, Eq. (4) is evaluated cell-by-cell to assess the local contribution to the variation of k_{eff} . The resulting local Δk_{eff} is presented in Figure 4 for both cases, where it is possible to appreciate strongly non-uniform distributions.

Figure 4. Percentage shape variation for each energy group flux for the Stand Alone Case (left) and Δk_{eff} distribution according to the perturbation theory for the Stand Alone (centre) and Coupled Case (right).

Specifically, the distribution exhibits most pronounced values at the core centre and at the boundary of the recirculation region. These peaks provide opposing contributions that effectively counterbalance one another, allowing for the onset of a new steady state at the end of the transient. In line with the ΔT distribution, the Δk_{eff} distribution is also more limited in the Coupled Case. This multidimensional effect arises from the combined influence of the temperature reduction within the recirculation region, in contrast to the temperature increase at the core centre, and the shape of neutron fluxes distributions, which are maximum in the central part of the core. During the transient, the reduction in power, generated and directly released into the coolant, is most significant at the core centre, corresponding to the largest attenuation of the neutron fluxes. Based on perturbation theory, global variations in the effective multiplication factor, Δk_{eff} , of -13.11 pcm and 2.08 pcm are obtained for the two cases, arising from the simplifying assumptions imposed in the perturbation theory application. Concerning numerical errors, time-step convergence tolerances of 10^{-5} for fluxes and 10^{-3} for temperature are set in OpenFOAM. Considering a thermal feedback coefficient $\alpha = -3.69$ pcm/K evaluated through the Monte Carlo code Serpent, these reactivity shifts correspond to temperature changes of about 3.55 K and -0.56 K, one or-

der of magnitude smaller than those observed in the simulations. Finally, a consideration is highlighted regarding the assumption $\varphi^* = \varphi$. First, the percentage variation in flux shape can be assessed by normalising the flux through a scaling factor based on the total flux. While the absolute flux level decreases sharply during the transient, the shape variation remains limited to below 3.5% across all energy groups. In addition, the shape variation in the delayed neutron precursor distribution remains below 1.5%. This result, shown for each flux group in Figure 4 for the Stand Alone Case, supports the validity of applying perturbation theory in the presented analysis.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work proposed an analysis to inspect the multidimensional effects related to the strong coupling between neutronics and thermal-hydraulics, inherent in the molten salt reactor concept. To meet this objective, multiphysics simulations in OpenFOAM were performed on a 2D axisymmetric wedge representing the primary loop of a MSFR, comparing the outcomes with a coupled OpenFOAM-Modelica case study. Specifically, the motivation stems from the results of a ULOHS transient simulation. The scenario is modelled through time-dependent functions imposed on global parameters of the primary heat exchanger in OpenFOAM and by a failure of the intermediate pump in the Coupled Case. At the end of the ULOHS transient, the mean core temperatures stabilise at different values with respect to the nominal ones, despite the absence of reactivity insertion, either from external sources or from delayed neutron precursor hold back. Also, the power and temperature levels are different for the two case studies, which impose different approaches to modelling the primary heat exchanger. To inspect these phenomena, the steady state solver was equipped with adjoint equations represented under the multigroup neutron diffusion approximation to retrieve the adjoint flux distributions at the beginning of the transient. Furthermore, perturbation theory was applied on a cell-by-cell basis in the domain to assess the local distribution of Δk_{eff} deriving from temperature variations, which affect the cross sections and diffusion coefficients in the neutronic submodule. The results highlighted the combined effect of a strongly non-uniform temperature variation and the neutron flux distribution established within the domain. The comparison between the two cases highlights that modelling the same transient using different approaches for the primary heat exchanger results in different temperature and power levels when converging to a new steady state condition. These aspects are related to the geometry of the domain and to the recirculation structure developing along the blanket wall due to the sharp edge at the core inlet. In principle, this effect could be mitigated through design optimisation aimed at preventing the formation of stagnation regions, which are also detrimental in terms of thermo-mechanical loads on the containment walls. Therefore, further investigations could be performed on progressively refined geometry. The proposed approach is, in principle, applicable to different reactor geometries, provided that neutronic feedbacks are consistently represented. In this study, precursor redistribution is neglected consistently to an imposed flow-rate scenario, under which precursor spatial variations remain limited. However, the framework can be extended to include reactivity contributions from delayed neutron precursor hold-back under varying flow rate conditions. Overall, these outcomes confirm the importance of analysing homogeneous reactor concepts such as the MSFR with multidimensional multiphysics modelling for an accurate evaluation of both steady state and transient reactor behaviour.

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